

Some New Protonated Ternary Complexes of Rare-Earths with CDTA/DTPA and Keto-Glutaric Acid**

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Potentiometric evidences have been cited for the formation of 1 : 1 : 1, M(III)-CDTA/DTPA-H₂KGA ternary complexes in the solution equilibria (where M(III) = La(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Gd(III) or Dy(III); CDTA = 1,2-diaminocyclohexanetetraacetic acid; DTPA = diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid and H₂KGA = β-ketoglutaric acid). Indications have been cited for the formation of protonated mixed ligand complexes at low pH as intermediate products, which undergo deprotonation at comparatively high pH forming 1 : 1 : 1, ternary species. The formation constants (log K_{MLL'}) for the protonated ternary species, formed by simultaneous addition of both the ligands to metal ion and their deprotonation constants -log K_A^H have been evaluated. The following order in the relative stabilities of the resulting complexes in terms of metal ions, La(III) < Pr(III) < Nd(III) < Gd(III) < Dy(III), has been observed.

THE biligand complexes of rare earths with one of the multidentate ligands such as NTA¹, HEDTA², EDTA³, CDTA^{4,5} or DTPA^{6,7} have been reported and in some of the cases an expansion in the coordination number of lanthanides have been suggested. Examples of polycentric⁸, hydroxo⁹ and protonated^{10,11} complexes of metals have also been reported in literature. Recently, Jahagirdar *et al*¹² have described the formation of ternary complexes of Nd(III) with dicarboxylic acids and glutaric acid as one of the ligands. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to investigate some more mixed ligand complexes of rare earths with hexadentate CDTA and octadentate DTPA ligands with bifunctional H₂KGA potentiometrically. The results of the formation of mixed ligand complexes through their intermediate protonated ternary species have been presented in this paper.

Experimental

Standard solutions of metal nitrates (BARC India), CDTA and DTPA (Fluka), KOH and KNO₃ (A.R. BDH) were prepared as described earlier^{1,5,6}. The solution of H₂KGA was prepared by direct weighing in double distilled water.

pH-metric titrations were carried out by Philips pH-meter (PR 9405) using standard glass (PV 9011) and calomel (PV 9021) electrode assembly. The instrument was standardised for pH=4 against 0.05M potassium hydrogenphthalate solution before each titration. The volume (50 ml), temperature (25 ± 1°), ionic strength (μ = 0.1M KNO₃) and concentration (5 × 10⁻³M) of the metal and the ligands were kept the same in every system. Each titration was repeated twice to ensure reproducibility of the measurements.

Calculations : The ionisation constants (pK₁ and pK₂) of the ligands H₂KGA (2.30, 5.12), K₂CDTA (11.22) and K₄DTPA (10.10) were calculated by the method of Chaberek and Martell¹³ and the formation constants (log K_{MLL'}) for the resulting ternary species were calculated by the method of Ramamoorthy and Santappa¹⁴. Considering the protonated mixed ligand complex present in equilibrium as a single species HA, its deprotonation constant (-log K_A^H) have been calculated from the following expressions as suggested by Dey *et al*¹⁵.

For the equilibrium

$$T_A = [HA^{n\pm}] + [A^{(n\pm)-1}] \quad \text{and} \quad (2)$$

$$A^{(n\pm)-1} = aT_A + [H^+] - [OH^-] \quad (3)$$

where HA^{n±} and A^{(n±)-1} are protonated and unprotonated species respectively; T_A represents the total concentration of HA^{n±} and (a) number of moles of base added per mole of HA^{n±}. From the equation 1, 2 and 3 the values of K_A^H can be calculated as :

$$K_A^H = \frac{[H^+][aT_A + [H^+] - [OH^-]]}{T_A - [aT_A + [H^+] - [OH^-]]} \quad (4)$$

Results and Discussion

The corresponding curves of all the systems studied were identical in nature. Only the curves representing the systems 1 : 1 : 1, La(III)-CDTA/DTPA-H₂KGA have therefore been discussed for the sake of brevity.

An inflection at m ~ 2.5 and the formation of a white gelatinous precipitate (curve a, Fig. 1) observed during the titration of La(III) nitrate may be

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Fig. 1. Curve a = La(III) nitrate, b = K_3 CDTA, c = H_2 KGA, d = 1 : 1, La(III)-CDTA, e = 1 : 1 La(III)- H_2 KGA, f = 1 : 1 : 1, La(III)-CDTA- H_2 KGA
 → Appearance of ppt.

Fig. 2. Curve b = K_4 DPTA, c = H_2 KGA, d = 1 : 1, La(III)-DPTA, e = 1 : 1, La(III)- H_2 KGA, f = 1 : 1 : 1, La(III)-DPTA- H_2 KGA
 → Appearance of ppt.

ascribed to basic-salt formation^{3,6}. Non-appearance of any inflection on curve b (Figs. 1 and 2) depicting the titration of K_3 CDTA and K_4 DPTA respectively, can be attributed to the non-titrable nature of the remaining carboxylic proton of CDTA and DTPA even at high pH. The occurrence of two well-defined inflections at $m=1$ and $m=2$ on curve c (Figs. 1 and 2) in the case of H_2 KGA, may be correlated to stepwise titration of the two carboxylic protons of the acid.

Binary systems : Curve d (Figs. 1 and 2) shows the titration of 1 : 1, La(III)-CDTA/DTPA binary mixture. A sharp inflection at $m=1$ and a sudden fall in the initial pH with the non-formation of any solid phase during the titration may be attributed to the formation of 1 : 1, La(III)-CDTA/DTPA soluble species. Curve e (Figs. 1 and 2) represents the titration of 1 : 1, La(III)- H_2 KGA binary system. The lowering in pH at the beginning and an inflection at $m=2$ can be attributed to the formation of 1 : 1, La(III)-KGA soluble complex. Another inflection at $m \sim 4$ may be correlated to the disproportionation of the initially formed 1 : 1 complex

into 1 : 3, with simultaneous precipitation of the remaining metal as its hydroxide :

Ternary systems : Curve f (Figs. 1 and 2) depicts the titration of 1 : 1 : 1, La(III)-CDTA/DTPA- H_2 KGA ternary systems respectively. The lowering in initial pH as compared to both the binary systems (curve d and e) and an inflection at $m=2$ probably correspond to the formation of protonated 1 : 1 : 1, ternary complex. The second inflection at $m=3$ in both the cases can be assigned to the deprotonation of the initially formed protonated species as described below taking DTPA as an example :

The formation of above ternary complex is further supported by (i) non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curve T^{17} in the region of mixed ligand complex formation, and (ii) absence of any solid phase during the titration of 1 : 1 : 1, La(III)-CDTA/DTPA- H_2 KGA ternary mixture.

In the pH-range (2.40-3.25) where the calculations for the protonated heteroligand species have been made, the H_2 KGA (dibasic acid) behaves as a mono-basic acid. The almost negligible value of percentage dissociation of the second proton of the acid (1.33%) at pH 3.25 as calculated by the method of Serjeant¹⁸ also supports the non-labile nature of the second proton of the H_2 KGA in the stated low pH-range during complex formation.

The calculated values of $\log K_{MLL'}(H)$ and $-\log K_2^H$ are recorded in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. The relative order of stabilities in terms of metal ions : La < Pr < Nd < Gd < Dy may be attributed to the decreasing size and increasing ionic potential (charge/radius ratio) of the metal ions. The slight lower values of $-\log K_2^H$ in comparison to the pK_2 of H_2 KGA is of significance and may be attributed

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS ($\log K_{MLL'}$) AT $25 \pm 1^\circ$

Metal ion	M(III)-CDTA- H_2 KGA	M(III)-DTPA- H_2 KGA
La(III)	4.23 ± 0.18	4.83 ± 0.15
Pr(III)	4.77 ± 0.17	4.92 ± 0.15
Nd(III)	4.94 ± 0.16	5.12 ± 0.13
Gd(III)	5.03 ± 0.14	5.88 ± 0.18
Dy(III)	5.25 ± 0.15	6.14 ± 0.18

to deprotonation of the ternary species having H_2KGA in coordinated state.

TABLE 2—DEPROTONATION CONSTANTS ($-\log K_A^H$)
OF THE TERNARY SPECIES AT $25 \pm 1^\circ$

Metal ion	M(III)-CDTA- H_2KGA	M(III)-DTPA- H_2KGA
La(III)	4.98 ± 0.03	4.96 ± 0.06
Pr(III)	4.95 ± 0.03	4.99 ± 0.05
Nd(III)	4.94 ± 0.04	4.97 ± 0.06
Gd(III)	4.92 ± 0.04	4.96 ± 0.05
Dy(III)	4.89 ± 0.04	4.95 ± 0.06

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